

VETERINARY SCIENCES

LIVER ENZYME PROFILES IN HIGH-YIELDING DAIRY COWS: INDICATORS OF METABOLIC HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

High-yielding dairy cows, particularly Holstein-Friesians, face significant metabolic challenges due to their genetic predisposition for high milk production, especially during the transition and peripartum periods. This review focuses on liver enzyme profiles as critical indicators of metabolic health, highlighting enzymes such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP). These biomarkers provide valuable insights into liver function, energy metabolism, and systemic health. The study examines the effects of factors such as nutrition, housing, environmental stress, and seasonal variations on the metabolic profiles of dairy cows. Additionally, the review emphasizes the importance of early detection of metabolic disorders through biochemical assessments, aiming to improve management strategies, enhance cow welfare, and optimize milk production. The findings underline the necessity of an integrated approach to minimize metabolic disorders and ensure sustainable dairy farming practices.

Keywords: liver enzymes, metabolic disorders, high-yielding dairy cows, biochemical profile, metabolic health.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, there has been a significant improvement in the genetic potential of high-yield dairy cows, which in our region has been evidenced by the import of Holstein-Friesian cattle. Holstein-Friesians are the largest of the dairy cattle breeds, known for their high milk yield and widespread popularity. This breed originated in the northern parts of the Netherlands, specifically North Holland and West Friesland. Initially, the cattle were either black and white or red and white. After 1750, farmers began exclusively selecting black and white bulls for breeding, leading to the predominance of this coloration, although the gene for the red color still exists. Grazing on the fertile lands of North Holland, these cattle were selectively bred for superior milk production. Through intensive selective breeding aimed at increasing milk production, the combined-friesian breed with good dairy characteristics has been developed into the highly dairy-focused Holstein-Friesian breed. The Holstein breed has a great potential for high milk yield, which can only be achieved under appropriate rearing conditions. In the last three decades, some Holstein-Friesian cows have produced over 27,000 kg of milk in a standard 305-day lactation cycle (Fuquay et al., 2011). In addition to high milk production, these cows are also expected to give birth to one healthy calf each year. The metabolism of high-yield dairy cows is often stressed due to their genetic predisposition for high milk production and reproductive demands. The increased energy requirements during pregnancy and lactation are frequently not matched by adequate energy intake, leading to functional disorders in various organs, most commonly the liver. Impaired liver function is associated with a higher incidence of metabolic disorders, reduced fertility, and immunosuppression, making the animals more susceptible to reproductive and infectious diseases (Vlasova and Saif,

2021). The metabolic strain on cows is most pronounced during the peripartum and transition periods. During lactation, there is a particularly high demand for metabolites used as precursors in the mammary gland for the synthesis of lactose, proteins, and milk fat. If these metabolites are not adequately supplied, the animal enters a state of negative energy balance, leading to various adverse effects (Tufarelli, et al., 2024). If these metabolites are not sufficiently provided, the animal falls into a negative energy balance, causing a range of adverse effects. External factors, such as diet and living conditions, impact metabolic processes. Poor nutrition, whether it leads to starvation or obesity, compromises liver function (McGuffey, 2017). As a consequence, there is a disruption in intermediate metabolism and an increased accumulation of fat in hepatocytes, commonly known as "fatty liver" (Chandler et al., 2023). Under conditions of inadequate nutrition, where laboratory analysis of the feed revealed that the silage was of very poor quality and contained excess butyric acid, and the alfalfa hay lacked sufficient nutrients due to improper cutting (low protein, high cellulose), Krnić and colleagues (1997) reported hyperbilirubinemia and hypotriglyceridemia, along with a tendency for reduced cholesterol and total protein levels, and increased aspartate aminotransferase activity in cows. Dairy cattle are prone to negative energy balance, particularly in the early lactation period when increased energy demands are not met with adequate intake. As a result, cows in negative energy balance mobilize adipose tissue to meet their energy needs. Excessive mobilization of adipose tissue is associated with reproductive and health problems (Mann, 2022).

The metabolic profile is particularly valuable in the study of high-yield dairy cows (Salamone et al., 2024). The metabolic strain on high-producing cows is most pronounced in late pregnancy and the postpartum

period. Metabolic disorders arise due to inadequate nutrition and imbalances between the intake and excretion of essential nutrients and metabolites, which are necessary for normal health, reproduction, and production capacity. Consequently, there has been increasing interest over the past decades in determining the metabolic profile to assess the nutritional and health status of cows. A significant number of subclinical deficiencies often lead to greater economic losses because they go unnoticed. Therefore, early identification of deficiency symptoms is crucial, as it allows for the quick correction of dietary errors. In this context, analyzing certain biochemical parameters in blood (serum and/or plasma) to determine the metabolic profile of cows can help not only in diagnosing but also in understanding the nature and severity of disorders within the body. Knowing the physiological values is particularly important in livestock farming, where it is used to evaluate the success of breeding and selection of animals, milk and meat production, and, more recently, to emphasize animal welfare (Phillips, 2024). Studies have been conducted on the impact of temperature and seasonal variations on the biochemical profile (Habeeb et al., 2023), as well as on the differences in biochemical profiles related to cattle breeds (Yang et al., 2022), and the influence of cows' physiological status on their biochemical profile (Sammad et al., 2020).

THE IMPORTANCE OF EXAMINING BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

Determining the values of specific physiological blood parameters allows for the timely detection of functional disorders in various organs and systems. Payne and colleagues (1970) were the first to highlight the importance of understanding metabolic profile values for diagnosing diseases. They introduced the so-called Compton test, which was quickly adopted by many experts. This test is based on the statistical assessment of blood biochemical parameters that can reveal early signs of disorders. By examining these biochemical parameters, it is possible to determine whether the tested animals (dairy cows) can maintain blood composition within physiological limits under different conditions of housing, nutrition, reproduction, and production. It also helps identify subclinical disease progression or explain the etiology of its onset (Cascone et al., 2022). The success of preventing metabolic diseases largely depends on timely and reliable diagnostics.

Interpreting the results of biochemical blood tests is a highly serious and complex procedure that requires a deep understanding of clinical physiology and biochemistry. It is important to note that no laboratory marker can unequivocally indicate a single disease, nor can any deviation be explained in just one way. Reference value ranges provide a framework for interpreting results and leave little room for doubt in the case of significant deviations.

However, minor deviations can be explained in multiple ways. For instance, transient hypoxia or increased metabolic activity of liver cells can lead to a slight increase in liver enzyme activity, just above the upper limit of reference values. Only with more severe hepatocyte necrosis would a significant deviation occur, which is easier to interpret. Similarly, elevated alkaline phosphatase activity in serum typically indicates

cholestasis. In young animals, this enzyme's activity is several times higher than in adults, and an increase in this value can result from rickets, osteomalacia, osteosarcoma (bone isoenzyme), or the administration of a single glucocorticosteroid injection (steroid-induced ALP isoenzyme).

The seasonal influence on the values of biochemical parameters in cows has been considered in the works of several authors (Guyot et al., 2024, Santos et al., 2024, Swaminathan et al., 2024, Dhaka et al., 2024, Hu et al., 2024). However, further research is necessary to fully understand these influences, as seasonal variations can significantly affect the health and productivity of cows, leading to more precise management and treatment strategies. The interpretation of laboratory test results should be approached with seriousness, considering all factors that might influence the outcome. It is essential to minimize the impact of such factors as much as possible.

BIOCHEMICAL PROFILE OF CATTLE

Although there are differences depending on the laboratory, the biochemical profile of ruminants typically includes the following parameters: glucose, urea, liver enzymes (alkaline phosphatase [AP], gamma-glutamyl transferase [GGT], and aspartate aminotransferase [AST]), bilirubin, minerals (calcium, phosphorus, and magnesium), serum proteins (total proteins and albumin), and muscle enzymes (creatine kinase and AST). In addition to these parameters, some laboratory analyses also measure lactate, creatinine, electrolytes (sodium, potassium, and chlorides), and total carbon dioxide (TCO₂). If needed, it is possible to determine bile acids, ammonia, cholesterol, and non-esterified fatty acids.

Liver Enzymes

The presence of certain intracellular enzymes in the blood can be a useful indicator of various diseases, provided their origin is reliably determined. Their presence in the blood usually indicates damage to specific cells and tissues. Some enzymes may be present in higher concentrations due to reversible disturbances in cell membrane permeability or increased cell function, such as during regenerative processes. Many clinically significant enzymes are found in cells of different organs, often in the form of various isoenzymes that can only be differentiated electrophoretically, making the interpretation of results quite complex.

The release of enzymes from cells primarily depends on their localization within the cells: cytoplasmic enzymes easily leave the cell during reversible disturbances in cell membrane permeability, such as liver hypoxia, making them sensitive indicators of minor damage, while mitochondrial enzymes are mostly released during cell lysis and thus indicate more severe damage. Many enzymes are present in both the cytoplasm and organelles simultaneously.

Alanine Aminotransferase

Alanine aminotransferase (ALT: EC 2.6.1.2) is a cytoplasmic enzyme, previously known as glutamate-pyruvate transaminase (GPT). This enzyme catalyzes the reversible transamination of alanine, resulting in the production of pyruvate, which can enter gluconeogenesis or the Krebs cycle. The primary mechanism leading to increased serum activity in domestic animals is

cellular damage, specifically damage to hepatocytes and skeletal myocytes. The serum level of ALT has been used as a marker for hepatocellular damage since the 1950s (Chimsky et al., 1956; Cornelius et al., 1958). Since ALT is a specific enzyme of liver cytosol, its increase in blood plasma is specific for liver changes. However, the activity of this enzyme in pigs, horses, goats, sheep, and cattle is not specific to the liver and is not clinically significant (Kramer and Hoffman, 1997). Other authors also report that serum ALT is a good indicator of hepatocellular necrosis, especially in dogs and cats, but it has less significance in horses, cattle, pigs, sheep, and goats (Underwood et al., 2015). Russell and Roussel (2007) state that ALT is used to assess hepatocellular damage in dogs and cats, while its levels in ruminants are low, and thus it is not significant for liver assessment in these species.

According to Kumar and Khurana (2002), no statistically significant difference in ALT levels was found between healthy cattle and those with dermatophytosis, while Atakisi et al. (2006) report that ALT levels significantly increase in cattle with dermatophytosis. The activity of ALT in blood plasma is influenced by age and muscle activity (Tufarelli et al., 2023)

Aspartate Aminotransferase

Aspartate aminotransferase (AST: EC 2.6.1.1), previously known as glutamate-oxaloacetate transaminase (GOT), is a cytoplasmic and mitochondrial enzyme that catalyzes reversible reactions involved in the deamination of aspartate, producing oxaloacetate, which enters the Krebs cycle. This enzyme is widely distributed in many tissues, with the highest activity found in the liver (Breda et al., 2023). AST, along with lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and L-iditol dehydrogenase (IDH), is commonly used to assess hepatocellular damage in ruminants. An increase in AST activity is a significant marker of liver damage (Škvareninová and Kostecká, 2023). There are two main isoenzymes: mitochondrial and cytosolic, with the mitochondrial isoenzyme dominating the total plasma concentration due to its longer half-life (Guyot et al., 2024). The primary mechanism leading to increased serum AST activity is cellular damage—affecting hepatocytes, skeletal myocytes, cardiac myocytes, and erythrocytes (Stockham and Scott, 2008). Although AST is a common marker for hepatocellular damage, its serum activity levels can also rise due to muscle injury, hemolysis, and other processes. Reversible or irreversible hepatocyte damage can occur due to various factors, including inflammation, hypoxia, and trauma. AST can be released from hepatocytes even during the reparative phase of liver diseases (Stockham and Scott, 2008). Increased activity can be observed in inflammatory conditions, both infectious and non-infectious. This includes bacterial hepatitis (Tyzzer's disease), bacterial cholangiohepatitis, infectious necrotic hepatitis, hepatic abscesses, and non-infectious conditions such as Theiler's disease, chronic hepatitis, and cirrhosis. It also follows toxic injuries (e.g., iron poisoning, aflatoxins, plants containing alkaloids, *Trifolium hybridum* poisoning) or metabolic liver disorders (e.g., lipidosis, diabetes mellitus). In chronic liver disease or slowly progressive liver conditions, enzyme activity may be at the lower end of or even below the reference range due to insufficient

hepatocyte damage or significantly reduced hepatocellular mass (Lechtenberg and Nagaraja, 1991). Therefore, these enzymes are more reliable indicators of acute conditions like infectious hepatitis or certain poisonings. Enzyme activity can be high in ruminants with hepatic lipidosis, passive venous congestion, and disorders leading to the distension of the fore-stomachs and abomasum. AST is often elevated in cases of abomasal volvulus and vagal indigestion, likely due to the pressure exerted on the liver by the distended organs (Proios and Grünberg, 2023). According to Kumar and Khurana (2002), there was no statistically significant difference in AST values between healthy cattle and those with dermatophytosis, whereas Atakisi et al. (2006) found significantly increased AST levels. The diagnostic sensitivity of AST activity in cattle is 94% for hepatic lipidosis, 100% for leptospirosis, 53% for hepatic abscesses, and 46% for fascioliasis (Hoffmann and Solter, 2008). Although AST is not a specific muscle enzyme, its levels increase with muscle tissue damage. However, when combined with creatine kinase (CK), it can be an important indicator of the extent of muscle damage. CK has a short serum half-life of about four hours (Loudon et al., 2019), while AST has a much longer half-life of approximately 20 hours (Stockham and Scott, 2008). Thus, AST activity rises and falls more slowly and, when used alongside CK values, can help evaluate muscle damage. In cattle that are down, AST activity higher than CK activity suggests damage that occurred several days ago. Certain myopathies also show increased ALT activity (Bermúdez et al., 2020).

Lactate Dehydrogenase

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH: EC 1.1.1.27) is a cytoplasmic enzyme that catalyzes the reversible conversion of pyruvate to lactate at the end of anaerobic glycolysis. LDH isoenzymes (proteins with different polypeptide structures that catalyze the same chemical reactions) are tetramers composed of heart subunits (H) or muscle subunits (M): LD-1 = HHHH, LD-2 = HHHM, LD-3 = HHMM, LD-4 = HMMM, LD-5 = MMMM. Identifying the specific isoenzyme responsible for increased total serum LDH activity would enhance its diagnostic value, but such identification requires specialized analyses that are not widely available. LDH is commonly used to diagnose liver diseases (Singh et al., 2021, Klein et al., 2020). The main mechanisms leading to increased LDH activity are cellular damage, including damage to hepatocytes, skeletal myocytes, cardiac myocytes, and erythrocytes. Increased serum LDH activity primarily indicates hepatocellular damage. However, serum LDH activity also rises in muscle damage and even mild hemolysis. Elevated LDH activity can result from reversible or irreversible, focal or diffuse cellular damage. To determine which tissue damage caused the enzyme levels to rise, LDH should be evaluated alongside other specific liver enzymes (such as GGT and IDH, formerly known as sorbitol dehydrogenase - SDH) and the muscle-specific enzyme creatine kinase (CK). Therefore, elevated AST or LDH activity with CK activity within physiological limits indicates liver disease. If CK levels are elevated, it suggests muscle tissue damage. If serum is left to stand with a clot for an extended period or if hemolysis is present, AST and LDH values can be falsely elevated

due to their release from erythrocytes (Farhana and Lappin, 2020). The activity of blood serum LDH was examined in seven calves during experimental sarcocystosis. The development of muscular cysts was associated with degenerative changes, including muscle fiber rupture and, in some cases, myositis. Sarcocysts can also cause liver damage, such as degenerative hepatitis. These processes lead to increased activity of several serum enzymes, including LDH and its isoenzymes. In calves, LDH activity remained stable until the 7th week after infection, after which it rose significantly, peaking at the 9th week post-infection. Similarly, the proportion of the LDH1 isoenzyme increased from the 7th week, reaching a maximum at the 9th week. Changes in the LDH isoenzyme profile, particularly the increase in liver-derived isoenzymes, indicate liver damage. The enzyme activity correlated with the progression of the disease. Indirect indicators of mastitis are crucial for diagnosing the subclinical form of the disease, which often lacks visible symptoms and carries significant economic implications. The diagnosis of subclinical mastitis (SCM) is challenging due to the absence of visible signs, making accurate detection methods essential. Several researchers have tested the use of soluble markers, particularly milk enzyme activities such as LDH, ALP, and AST, to identify udder infections in dairy cows (Bogin et al., 1977). Zank and Schlatterer (1998) highlighted that cell-damaging processes during mammary inflammation are best detected by elevated LDH activity. Kováč and Beseda (1975) studied the total LDH activity in the milk serum of dairy cows with varying responses to mastitis tests. They found a proportional increase in total LDH activity in milk serum correlating with the degree of positive responses to mastitis tests. Bogin and Ziv (1973) suggested that LDH in milk serves as a sensitive indicator of epithelial cell damage, originating mainly from damaged udder epithelial cells and increased leukocyte populations. Authors identified LDH isoenzyme patterns in normal and mastitic bovine udder tissues and milk. The increased proportion of LDH4 and LDH5 isoenzymes in inflamed tissues and mastitic milk leukocytes suggests that the elevated LDH activity originates from leukocytes and udder parenchymal cells (Klein et al., 2020). Hiss and associates (2007) quantified LDH activity in milk samples from healthy and subclinically diseased udder quarters, finding a positive correlation between somatic cell count (SCC) and LDH activity. This makes LDH activity a useful parameter for diagnosing subclinical mastitis. However, udder quarters with latent infections and normal SCC could not be distinguished from healthy quarters using LDH activity. Yang et al. (2011) found significantly higher LDH activity in SCM milk compared to normal milk, further supporting the use of LDH as a diagnostic tool for SCM. Chagunda et al. (2006) studied the relationship between LDH and N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase (NAGase) activities, SCC, and udder health status. They concluded that LDH activity was more sensitive than NAGase activity and was robust to changes in threshold values. Vyavahare et al. (2009) investigated LDH activity in milk-whey and blood plasma associated with udder health status, finding significant differences in LDH activity

among different udder health statuses, with no differences in blood plasma. This indicates that LDH activity in milk-whey is useful for assessing udder health status in cows. Mohammadian (2011) examined the relationship between LDH activity and SCM in dairy herds, finding higher LDH activity in milk from udders affected by SCM compared to healthy udders. There were no significant differences in blood serum LDH activity between healthy and SCM-affected cows, suggesting that the increased LDH activity in mastitic milk originates primarily from damaged udder epithelial cells and increased leukocytes. Nizamlioglu and Erganis (1991) found a significant positive correlation between LDH activity and SCC in Merino ewes, confirming LDH as a sensitive and specific indicator of subclinical mastitis in ewes. Atroshi et al. (1996) reported elevated LDH activity in mastitic cows, indicating that increased LDH activity reflects inflammatory changes or trauma to udder tissue. Moreover, increased LDH activity during experimental mastitis in goats has been linked to the degree of inflammation (Koul et al., 1993). Multiple studies have demonstrated that LDH activity in milk from udders with SCM is significantly higher than in milk from healthy udders. The presence of elevated LDH in milk may be attributed to damage to blood-milk barriers during infection, allowing LDH to transfer from blood to milk. Batavani et al. (2003) suggested that blood serum is not the sole source of LDH in mastitic milk, as it may also be derived from udder parenchymal cells and disintegrated leukocytes.

Alkaline Phosphatase

Alkaline phosphatase (ALP: EC 3.1.3.1) refers to phosphatases that are active in an alkaline environment, in contrast to acid phosphatases, which are active in an acidic environment. Their role is to hydrolyze phosphate monoesters (Le-Vinh et al., 2022). ALP primarily originates from the intestinal mucosa, kidneys, bones, and liver (Lowe et al., 2023). The physiological role of ALP varies among tissues. For instance, liver ALP (L-ALP) is involved in dephosphorylating bacterial endotoxins, thereby reducing their toxic effects (Balabanova et al., 2024), while bone ALP (B-ALP) is involved in bone mineralization (Shu et al., 2022). ALP is considered a marker of bone proliferation, and increased enzyme activity is seen in bone metabolism disorders (Ansari et al., 2022). ALP exhibits activity across a diverse range of organisms, spanning from bacteria to mammals, and is often described as possessing "catalytic promiscuity." This characteristic may have facilitated its widespread evolutionary presence and ubiquitous distribution. Despite being one of the most extensively studied enzymes, the physiological role of ALP remains only partially understood. In mammals, ALP exists in a soluble form in serum and is also located on various cellular membranes throughout the body (Fernandez and Kidney, 2007). Although ALP activity is present in many cells and tissues, the highest activity is found in the liver, bones, kidneys, intestinal mucosa, and placenta (Lowe et al., 2023). Most ALP is located in the cell membrane of hepatocytes (Valocky et al., 2007). Serum ALP activity does not reflect its concentration in tissues. In most domestic animals, intestinal ALP cannot be detected in serum, and the liver accounts for more than half of total serum activity. ALP

activity increases in liver and muscle diseases and decreases during diarrhea and with animal aging (Kraft and Dürr, 2013). Age-related decreases in ALP activity in cows have been noted by Shaffer et al. (1981), Rousset et al. (1982), and Otto et al. (2000). In calves from birth to 83 days of age, total serum ALP activity is elevated compared to adult levels. ALP activity is highest at birth, reaching up to five times the level observed in adults, and then decreases within 10 days to approximately three times adult values. ALP isoforms were not identified, although a separate study demonstrated the presence of kidney-derived ALP in neonatal calf serum (Fernandez and Kidney, 2007). The profile of ALP isoforms continues to shift throughout an organism's lifespan. In healthy dogs without systemic disease or a history of steroid therapy, variations in the proportion of bone, corticosteroid-induced, and liver-derived ALP activity were observed with increasing age. Increased ALP production by hepatocytes has been observed in cholestasis. The enzyme's activity increases secondarily to biliary obstruction caused by fascioliasis or cholelithiasis (Russell and Rousset, 2007). ALP activity also rises in conditions such as hyperparathyroidism, hyperthyroidism, osteodystrophy, malignant bone tumors, fractures, rickets, osteomalacia, and periostitis (Boonprong et al., 2007). Physiological increases in ALP activity occur during growth and pregnancy (Šoch et al., 2008). In pregnant human females, the activity of the placental isoenzyme of ALP (placental ALP) is elevated, leading to increased serum ALP activity. In the last trimester, this increase can be up to four times the normal level. Serum ALP activity returns to reference intervals within 20 days postpartum. Elevated placental ALP activity has also been observed in the serum of pregnant queens and, possibly, pregnant cows, but not in pregnant bitches or mares. In queens, placental ALP generally does not contribute significantly to total ALP activity due to its short half-life in serum (less than 2 minutes). However, placental ALP activity has been detected in serum during late pregnancy. It remains unclear whether the increased placental ALP activity contributes to the overall rise in total serum ALP activity, or if total serum ALP levels remain within reference intervals. In pregnant cows, an increase in total serum ALP activity is observed in mid and late pregnancy, likely driven by increased placental ALP activity, though ALP isoforms have not been identified. Serum ALP activity is also influenced by lactation and pregnancy stages. In lactating dairy cows, serum ALP activity increases due to elevated bone and liver ALP activity. Serum ALP activity peaks in early lactation and gradually declines thereafter. Mammary gland-derived ALP is present in milk, but its contribution to serum ALP activity remains unclear, as it cannot be distinguished from bone-derived ALP using current isoform detection methods. Serum ALP activity also exhibits seasonal variation in cows, independent of reproductive status. In humans, increased intestinal ALP activity following meals can result in up to a fivefold increase in serum ALP levels, particularly in individuals consuming a high-fat diet. Typically, less than 10% of serum ALP activity originates from the intestine, but after consuming fat-rich meals, up to 92% of serum ALP activity may be attributed to the intestinal isoenzyme. In

contrast, intestinal ALP does not contribute to serum ALP activity in domestic animals. ALP activity is of limited utility in cattle due to its wide reference interval, which is often established without considering the stage of lactation, a factor that significantly influences serum ALP levels in dairy cows

CONCLUSION

Understanding liver enzyme profiles in high-yielding dairy cows is essential for managing their metabolic health and ensuring sustainable productivity. These cows, particularly susceptible to metabolic and liver dysfunctions due to their genetic predisposition and high energy demands, benefit significantly from regular biochemical assessments. Key enzymes such as ALT, AST, LDH, and ALP provide critical insights into hepatocellular damage, energy metabolism, and overall systemic health. Monitoring these markers is crucial for identifying subclinical disorders early and preventing their progression to more severe health issues. The findings of this review highlight the complex interaction between genetics, nutrition, environmental factors, and animal management in influencing metabolic stability. Factors like suboptimal nutrition, poor housing conditions, and stress during the transition period are major contributors to liver dysfunction and metabolic disorders. A holistic management approach, incorporating precision feeding strategies, optimal living conditions, and regular metabolic monitoring, is fundamental to minimizing these risks. Future advancements in diagnostic methodologies, particularly the identification of novel and more sensitive biomarkers, hold promise for more effective health monitoring in dairy cows. Additional research on the influence of seasonal variations, stress, and emerging metabolic markers could further enhance our ability to maintain optimal health and productivity in these animals. By integrating proactive management strategies with ongoing research and technological innovation, dairy producers can better safeguard the welfare of high-yielding cows while ensuring the economic sustainability of their operations.

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